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CONTENT

**A RE - EXAMINATION OF THE IMPACT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP
DEVELOPMENT ON ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENTS IN NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

The objectives of this study are to examine the influence of entrepreneurship development as it affect economic development, examine the various policies of government to promote the development and growth of entrepreneurship and examine the employment creation potentials of the small and medium enterprises

In order to achieve the objectives a comprehensive examination of the various government policies were undertaken bearing in mind the year and purpose of their establishment. In addition a survey of 375 small business owners were undertaken to determine the nature of business they operate and the average number of people employed. The study revealed that about 43.33% and 21.33% were in service and manufacturing activities respectively. Also about 63.7% employed between 1-9, and 32.8% employed between 10-50. It is obvious from the study that micro/cottage industry dominate the economy, government policies should therefore be made more favourable to the operators in this sector

Introduction:

The need for entrepreneurship initiative in Nigeria emanates from the social, political and economic environment and its prevailing conditions.

Social changes in Nigeria had created the need for the development of entrepreneurship initiative as it has become obvious that various successive government at all levels can no longer adequately provide for the multifaceted needs of the ever increasing population. The past neglect of the rural development has brought about consistent and continuous migration from the rural areas to the urban centres with it associated increase in the crime rates as a result of non availability of gainful employment in the urban centres. The current food crisis can also be linked to this same problem.

The current level of economic difficulties in Nigeria such as low wage rate, high level of inflation and financial hardship show the need for income generating activities such as small scale industries to help alleviate poverty. The need to reduce the level of unemployment, diversify the economic base, improve standard of living of the people, build a self reliant and self-sustaining economy have created the need for entrepreneurship development. The problem stated thus far can be addressed by entrepreneurship development.

The major objectives of this study is to examine the impact of entrepreneurship development as it affect the economic development of Nigeria. Other objectives include:

- i. To investigate the various policies of government put in place to encourage entrepreneurs initiative.
- ii. To examine the contribution of entrepreneurship to the employment generation/creation in Nigeria.
- iii. Finally to make necessary recommendations to the policy makers as well as the practitioners.
- iv. The study will provide answer to the following research questions:
 - v. What are the policies government have put in place to encourage the development of entrepreneurship?
 - vi. What are the contributions of the medium and small scale enterprises to the economic development in terms of employment generation.

The paper is divided into five sections, section one introduced the paper, while two and three deals with the theoretical and methodology respectively, section four present results and discussion while section five presented the summary of findings, recommendations and conclusion.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Evolution and Definitions of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneur is a French word which is literally translated "between-taker" or "go-between" (Hisrich & Peter 1995), "to undertake" Kuratko & Hudgett (2007). The coming of the term entrepreneur was associated to Richard Cantillon an economist in 18th century France who associated the risk-bearing activity in the economy with the entrepreneur.

Until the 1950s the majority of definitions and references to entrepreneurship had been associated to the economists like Richard Cantillon, 1725; Jean Baptiste Say 1803; and Joseph Schumpeter 1934 (Kuratko & Hodgett 2007).

Survey of Entrepreneurship Definitions

There is no single acceptable definition of entrepreneurship in the literature, the term is quite illusive to define and this because it is a multidisciplinary construct. Each academic discipline tends to define the term considering their academic backgrounds. Hisrich & Peter 1995 and Kuratko & Hodgett 2007 compiled the following definitions. For example Vesper (1980 p.2) looked at entrepreneurship from different backgrounds he says "To an economist, an entrepreneur is one who brings resource, labour, materials and other assets into combination that make their value greater than before, and also one who introduces changes innovations and a new order. To a psychologist, such a person is typically driven by certain forces- need to obtain or attain something, to experiment, to accomplish or perhaps to escape authority of others.... To one businessman the same entrepreneurship may be an ally, a source of supply, a customer, or someone good to invest in..... The same person is seen by a capitalist philosopher as one who creates wealth for others as well who funds better ways to utilize resources and reduce waste and who produce jobs, others are glad to get' Entrepreneurship is the dynamic process of creating incremental wealth.

The wealth is created by individuals who assume the major risks in terms of equity, time, and/or career commitment or provide value for some product or services. The product or service may or may not be new or unique but value must somehow be infused by the entrepreneur by receiving and locating the necessary skills and resources. (Rostadt, 1984 p. 28)

Entrepreneurship is the process of creating something different with value by devoting the necessary time and effort assuming the company financial, psychic, and social risks, and receiving the resulting rewards of monetary and personal satisfaction and independence. - Histrich & Peter 1995 p. 10

Enterpereneurship consists in doing things that are not generally done in the ordinary course of business routine; it is essentially a phenomenon that comes under the wider aspect of leadership (Joseph Schumpeter 1951 p. 255)

Enterpereneurship at least in all non authoritarian societies, constitutes a bridge between society as whole, especially the non economic aspects of that society, and the profit-oriented institutions established to take advantage of its economic endowments and to satisfy as best they can, its economic desires. (Authur Cole 1959 pp 27-28).

In...entrepreneurship, there is agreement that we are talking about a-kind of behaviour that includes (1) Initiative taking (2) the organizing or reorganizing of social economic mechanisms to turn resources and Situations to practical account and (3) the acceptance of risk of failure.

Shapero 1975p. 187.

Entrepreneurship is a dynamic process of vision change and creation. It requires an application of energy and passion toward the creation and implementation of new ideas and creative solutions. Essential ingredients include the willingness to take calculated risks-in terms of time, equity, or career; the ability to formulate an effective venture team; the creative skill in marshal needed resources; the fundamental skill of building a solid business plan; and , finally, the vision to recognise opportunity where others see chaos, contradiction and confusion.' (Kuratko & Hodget 2007 p. 33).

The common features of most of the definitions above show that entrepreneurship endeavours involves among others:

- Resources coordination
- Changes and innovation
- Creativity and creation of wealth
- Achievement needs
- Risk taking

- Initiative
- Passion and energy

For the purpose of the study Kuratko Hodgett 2007 definition will be adopted as the working definition as it takes into consideration various elements in the other definitions. This is not to say it is the best but for our purpose.

CHARACTERISTICS OF ENTREPRENEURS

The characteristics of an entrepreneur is another aspect where literature is divided. Where there is agreement, the extent of the variable on the entrepreneurship success also becomes a subject of controversy.

Longenecker, Moore and Petty (1997) listed the following as the characteristic of an entrepreneur:

- Need for achievement Willingness to take risks
- Self confidence
- A need to seek refuge

Kao (1991) identified eleven (11) characteristics of an entrepreneurs namely: total commitment, determination and perseverance; drive to achieve and grow; opportunity and goal orientation; taking initiative and personal responsibility; persistent problem solving; realism and a sense of humour; seeking and using feedback; internal focus of control; calculated risk taking and risk seeking; low need of status and power and integrity and reliability. Hornadey (1982) in a survey of literature came up with about forty-two (42) characteristics often attributed to entrepreneur.

Considering the various characteristics of an entrepreneur identified in the literature, an important conclusion can be reached according to Nkamnabe (2003) that entrepreneurship represents an important economic event, which is central in the economic development of individuals and nation"

ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

The importance of entrepreneurship development in economic development has been an established fact in the literature. Ritter (1998) painted this picture about entrepreneurs and economic development thus:

"Entrepreneurship is scarce for many types of economic activities in most countries and at most times, particularly for new activities requiring relatively new types of technical and market knowledge. The contribution of entrepreneurship to the process of economic development is clear. Entrepreneurs are dynamic force in an economy, envisioning the possibilities of new types of economic activity and doing everything necessary to realize their visions. As a result, entrepreneurs give birth to new enterprises, new commercial activities and new economic sectors. They generate jobs for others; they produce goods and services for citizens; they introduce new cost-cutting or product-improving production technologies and improved or lower-cost outputs; they earn foreign exchange through exports expansion or the substitution of imports; they save, raise funds, and invest. They also generate the income and wealth that permit the collection of taxes by governments for expenditure on human development (education, health, and social services), physical infrastructure and public goods generally. They promote the process of learning and adapting to changing circumstances as technology changes, market evolve; and policies change"

Recognizing the important roles of entrepreneurs, both developed and developing nations have shifted attention to their development. The need to create and ensure appropriate environment for operations of the enterprises cannot be over emphasised.

Ritter (1998) noted that for entrepreneurship to operate developmental way the institutional environment, the system of laws, the regulatory environment, and basic political and economic stability have to exist and consistent, the absence of the enabling environment will deform the entrepreneurs. Nnanna (2003) acknowledged that SMEs are the bedrock of the industrial development, they provided large scale employment as they are often labour intensive and they rely more heavily on local raw materials. Zakar (2006) classified the benefits of SMEs and entrepreneurs into three broad categories benefits to the nation, benefits to the society and benefits to the individual. Olayiwola and Ogundele (2008) also pointed out

the roles of entrepreneurs as engine of growth and development. The study pointed the following roles among setting corporate ethical standards

Corporate ethical behaviour involves both knowing what is right and wrong and behaving accordingly. Ethical emphasis standards of moral behaviour, that is behaviour that is accepted by society as right versus wrong. Organizational ethics begins at the top hence entrepreneurs must uphold high ethical standard since behaving ethically have a positive influence on the success of the business. Although ethical codes vary greatly, they can be broadly classified as compliance-based and integrity-based. Compliance-based ethics codes emphasize preventing unlawful behaviour, by increasing control and by penalizing wrong doers. While on the other hand, integrity-based ethics codes defines the organization's guiding values, create an environment that supports ethically sound behaviour, and stress a shared accountability among

Employment Creation

Secondly the entrepreneur is expected to create employment for the increased population and also to prevent rural-urban drift (Olayiwola2007). This will also reduce the high rate of criminal activities in the economy and bring about secured society

Improve Standard of Living.

Thirdly the entrepreneurs are expected to improve the standard of living of the people through quality products/services as also through a well motivated workforce employed by the MSMEs. Improving standard of living must be the responsibility of the entrepreneurs as healthy people will bring about a wealthy economy.

Increase in government Revenues

Fourthly entrepreneurs will also bring about an increase in the government revenues in the areas of value added taxes, company income taxes and income taxes of the employees of these small businesses.

Utilization of local resources

The domestic entrepreneurs are also expected to look more inward by sourcing for the raw material locally and rely more on the employment of domestic experts.

Development of domestic /Indigenous technology

The entrepreneurs are also expected to develop indigenous industrial machinery and equipment, evolve a management approach in consonance with the indigenous culture. Most technologically advanced countries also started from some where.

Supplier of raw material for larger industries

The entrepreneurs should also provide the larger industries with raw materials for the expanded output this will reduce the cost of production reduce the price level and increase the level of economic welfare

METHODOLOGY

The study basically made use of a survey research jointly carried out by the writer and an undergraduate research project student. A well structured questionnaire were administered to find out the nature of business the entrepreneurs were engaged in, the number of employees that were currently engaged. In addition a survey of 375 small business owners were undertaken to determine the nature of business they operate and the average number of people employed. Relevant secondary data were also used particularly to point out the various policies of government to encourage the growth and development of entrepreneurship. The methodology was adapted due to the shortness of the time duration within which this study must be presented. The various questions raised in the study were answered on the basis of the data collected from the various agencies as well as research findings in Nigeria.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section present the results of the study presenting using each objectives earlier stated as the guide.

Policies of Government/Other Agencies to encourage Entrepreneurship Development

TABLE 1 Policies and Programme to promote SMEs

1	Small Scale Industries Credit Guarantee Scheme	1971	As a matching grant arrangement between the federal and state government. (1) to provide technical and financial supports for SMEs (2) to make credit available in liberal terms to SMEs.
2	Nigeria Industrial Development Bank Ltd (NIDB) 1962 (already merged with Bank of Industry).	1962	Primary mandate of: Providing medium and long term loans for investment in industrial activities It focuses more on large enterprises which has a special units focusing on SMEs financial requirements Was responsible for the bulk of credit delivery to the SME under SME II loan scheme
3	The Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industry (NBCI) (now part of Bank of Industry)	1973	To provide among other things Financial services to the indigenous business community. Particularly SME It operates as apex financial body for the SME and also administered the SME and owned bank loan scheme.

4	Rural Banking Scheme	1977	Designed to solve problem of rural under development Inadequate of credit to the agricultural sector and rural based small scale industries
5	Agricultural Credit 1978 Guarantee Scheme Fund		To facilitate the accessibility of credit to the agricultural sector Federal government and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) jointly owned the scheme.
6	Credit Guidelines in the annual Monetary policy circular issued by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) between January 1979 and October 1996	January 1979- October 1996	This required banks to allocate stipulated minimum credit to the preferred sectors of the economy including SMEs.
7	National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND)	1980	provision of long term loan (5 10 years) to SME at concessional rates of interest.
8	Peoples Bank of Nigeria	October 1989	Meeting the credit needs of the very small (micro) enterprises Loans of the banks administer to groups of entrepreneurs rather than individuals on a deliberate policy based on the "peer pressure" concept.

9	World Bank SME I Loan Scheme	1990	<p>It aimed at expanding credit delivery to SMEs. (A loan of \$270 million lent out to SMEs).</p> <p>Fiscal incentives in the form of:</p> <p>Tax relief to all SMEs during the first six years of operation</p> <p>Pioneer status involving non-renewable tax relief for five years</p> <p>Periodic downward adjustment of tariffs to reduce production cost</p> <p>Second tier window on the capital market designed to accommodate small enterprise that cannot satisfy the listing requirements on the main window (first tier window)</p>
10	Nigeria Export Import Bank (NEXIM)	1991	<p>To provide finances, risk mitigating facilities and trade information as well as advisory services to Nigerian exporters</p> <p>Assistance to exportable industrialist</p>
11	Small and Medium became Industries Equity operational Investment Scheme Initiated in	2001	<p>Community Banks 1991 to promotion of rural development by providing financial and bank services to communities inadequately supplied with such services.</p> <p>Bankers committees agreed to set aside 10% of their profits before tax annually for equity investment in small and medium industries as their contribution to</p>

			<p>government efforts towards stimulating economic growth.</p> <p>Developing local technology and generating employment.</p> <p>It aims at partnering between banks and promoters of industry.</p>
12	Nigerian Agricultural Cooperative and Rural Development Bank (NACRDB)	October 2000	<p>It is the amalgamation of :</p> <p>Peoples Bank of Nigeria</p> <p>Nigerian Agricultural and Cooperative Bank</p> <p>Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP)</p> <p>Objective to finance agriculture as well as small and medium enterprises</p> <p>It can accept deposit and offer loans/advances.</p>
13	Bank of Industry	2000	<p>Amalgamation of Nigerian Bank for Commerce and Industry</p> <p>National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND)</p> <p>Objectives: Providing sector, including SMEs.</p>
14	Refinancing and Rediscountin Facility	January 2002	<p>CBN introduced the concessional interest rate to support medium to long term bank lending to the productive sectors of the economy.</p>

			It is to provide sectors of the economy. Support of their financing of real sector activities.
15	The National Directorate of Employment (NDE)	1986	NDE landed a number of program to generate self-employment or : Small scale industries Youth employment and vocational skills development Special public works. Two credit schemes were also operated namely. Graduate Job Creation Loan Scheme (GILS) The Matured People's Scheme (MPS) Facilities under the two schemes are paid over a five year with varying periods of moratorium.

There are other policies that are also put in place by the various States and Local Government to support private initiatives such as State-owned finance and investment which provided technical and financial assistance to SMEs. Other channels through which government has promoted the development of SMEs include International financial Assistance; the Second Tier Securities Market

Other Technical Training and Extension Services Programmes such as Industrial Training Fund (ITF); Raw Materials Research and Development Council (RMRDC); Federal Institute of Industrial Research, Oshodi (FIIRO) Project Development Agency (PRODA) and Center for Management Development to mention a few. Olorunshola (2003) attempted a critical appraisal of the various policies.

In the appraisal it was pointed out that while some achieved a minimum level of success others are complete failure. Various reasons were given for the low performance of the SMEs despite several measures put in place to facilitate its growth. The studies of Olorunsola (2003) and Anyawu

(2003) identified the following problems and constraints: inadequate infrastructural facilities; continued restricted access to credit; shortage of skill; financial indiscipline; poor implementation policies; poor management practices and low entrepreneurial skill; overbearing regulatory and operational environment and abuse of the various programmes by both the beneficiaries and the operators arising from insincerity of purpose among others.

Employment Generation of the SMEs and Nature of Business

In a survey of 375 small and medium enterprises recently conducted by Olorunjobi and Olayiwola (2008) at the Oshodi-Isolo Local Government area of Lagos State, the table below shows the distribution of the respondents according to the nature of activities

Table 2 Nature of SMEs activities

Nature of Business	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Manufacturing	80	21.33
Service	155	43.33
Construction	55	14.67
Others	85	22.67
Total	375	100

The study revealed that there is high concentration of SMEs activities in the service industry. The service industry in the study includes buying and selling of all kinds of goods and services. It accounted for 43.33% of the total response while manufacturing and construction accounted for 21.33 and 14.67 respectively. All other activities are categorised as others and it accounted for 22.67%

The study further examined the level of employment generated by these small and medium enterprises as shown in the table 3 below

Table 3 Number of staff employed by SMEs

Number of Staff employed	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1-9	239	63.73
10-50	123	32.80
21-100		2.13
101-150	3	0.80
151-200	1	0.27
201-above	1	0.27
Total	375	100

The survey showed that 239 representing 63.73% of the SMEs employed between 1-9 while 125 or 32.8% employed between 10-50. By the definitions of Micro/ Cottage Industry as an industry with a labour size of not more than ten (10) workers, or total cost of not more than #1.5million, including working capital but excluding cost of land. Small Scale Industry as an industry with labour size of between 11-100 or a total cost of not more than #50million, including working capital but excluding cost of land.

Medium Scale Industry as an industry with a labour size of between 101-300 workers or a total cost of over #50 million but not more than #200 million, excluding working capital bur excluding cost of land. It is obvious that majority of the so call small businesses are actually micro/cottage industry.

The study of Ogunleye (2000) also supported this findings as shown in the table 4 below as it revealed that given the definitions above most industries in Nigeria will be classified as Micro/cottage industry as the number of employees are rather low.

Table 4 Distribution of Establishment by Activity Group and by size (Nigeria)

	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	NE	Total	
Activity Group	0-4	5-9	10-19	20-49	50-99	100-199	200-499	500-999	1000+	No	%
Agric & forestry	5	693	364	276	92	47	25	6	7	1513	2.58
Min. & Quar.	3	60	37	50	16	10	2	1	4	183	0.31
Manufacturing	130	11352	3012	1224	341	202	172	58	51	16542	28.20
Electricity, gas & water	5	73	31	43	20	8	10	1	3	194	0.33
Building & Contr	24	311	144	136	62	33	33	11	7	761	1.30
Wholesale & retail Trade	179	7522	1944	541	94	42	12	10	0	10344	17.63
Hotel & Restaurant	46	3301	931	258	52	30	9	6	0	4633	7.90
Land Transport	9	355	208	111	29	21	9	0	0	742	1.26
Other Transport	7	192	108	67	16	14	4	3	0	411	0.70
Private Prof. Services	1546	3437	1699	893	170	48	23	4	3	7823	13.34
Other Services	854	10512	3061	814	144	77	39	11	7	15519	26.45
Total NO	2808	37808	11539	4411	1036	532	338	111	82	58665	100
%	4.79	64.45	19.67	7.52	1.77	0.91	0.58	0.19	0.14	100.0	

Source: Ogunleye, G.A. (2000) 'Small and Medium Scale Enterprises as Foundation for Rapid

Economic Development in Nigeria NDIC QUARTERLY Vol 10 NO 4 Key: NE Number of Employees

Table 4 above reveals the number of establishment by activity group and by employment size in Nigeria. Looking at the earlier definition proposed by the National Council on Industry about 69.24% will fall within the micro/cottage industry; 28.76% small scale while only 1.49% will be categorised as medium scale industry. The table clearly revealed that for any meaningful development to take place government need favourable policies that will encourage the development of the MSMEs. The total contribution of MSMEs to the employment generation was in excess of 99%.

CONCLUSION

The study emphasised the importance of entrepreneurship development to the economic development. It gave a brief evolution of the word entrepreneur and a brief survey of the various definitions. The study also examined the various policies of government to promote the development of the SMEs in Nigeria. Reasons for non effectiveness were listed. In addition the employment generation potentials were discussed. in the sty revea are mainy microcoitage

industry, service industry, and buying and selling are the common business in the study area, employment opportunity were provided by both service and manufacturing industry.

On the basis of the findings it is hereby recommended that the governments at all levels should set up a small and medium enterprises commission that will be responsible to re-appraise the past policies with the aim of reviving the viable ones and ensure their effective implementations. In addition, since the majority of businesses operating in Nigeria are micro and small businesses, the regulatory environment should be made to be more friendly with the operators. According to Kuratko & Hodgett (2007) special regulations are made to small business owners which reduce stiff regulatory requirements to large industry in the United States of America.

Finally to foster a vibrant and competitive entrepreneurship development that we enhance job creation, promote economic growth and development, reduce poverty and create wealth there is need to make finance easily accessible to small business owners so as to enable the diversification of According to Nichols et al (2002) small business create 75% of the new jobs in America, account for more than 40% of the gross domestic product and more than 80% of Americans find their first job in small businesses. If the enabling environment is made conducive, the small businesses in Nigeria can operate at the same level in their contribution to the national economy and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Anyawu, C. M. 2003 'The role of Central Bank of Nigeria in Enterprises Financing' Central Bank of Nigeria Training Centre Lagos No 4 pp. 20-32
- Hisrich R.D. & Peters M.P. 1995 Entrepreneurship: Starting Developing and Managing a New Enterprise 3rd ed. USA: Richard D. Irwin Inc.
- Hornaday, J. (1982)Research about Living Entrepreneurs" in Encyclopedia of Entrepreneurship ed Calving Kent Donald Sexton and Karl Vester pp 26 27.
- Kao, J.J. (1991) The Entrepreneur Englewood Cliffs N J; Prentice Hall.
- Kurtatko D.F. & Nodgetts 2007 Entrpreneurship: Theory Process Practice 7th ed. United States: Thomson South-Western pp. 37-41
- Longnecker J.G. ;Moore C.W.&Petty, J W 1997 Small Business Management: An Entrepreneurial Emphasis Cincinnati Ohio: SouthWestern College Publishing
- Nkamnebe, Anayo D. 2003 'Entrepreneurial Training and Development in Africa: Reflections on Critical Issues from Nigeria', in Dimension of African Business and Development Nwankwo, S; Montanheiro L; Aiyeku and Ogbuehi, A ;eds Sheffied Hallam University, Sheffield, United Kingdom pp. 151-166
- Nichels W.G, James M. McHuGH & Susan M. McHUGH 2002 Understanding Business 6th ed.Boston: McGraw-Hill Companies Inc. Pp164-199
- Nanna, O.J.(2003. The Role of Central Bank of Nigeria in Enterprises Financing (Central Bank Nigeria, 27(1).
- Ritter, A.R.M 1998 Entrepreneurship, MicroEnterprise and Public Policy in Cuba: Promotion, Containment, or Asphyxiation? Journal of Interamencan Studies and World Affairs vol. 40 No. 2 Summer pp 63 94.
- Ogundele, O. J.K. 2007 Entrepreneurship Development Corporate Governance and Small Business Management, Lagos; Molofin Nominees
- Ogunleye, G. A. 2000 Small and Medium Scale Enterprises As Foundation For Rapid Economic Development In Nigeria NDIC QUARTERLY Vol. 10 No 4
- Olayiwola P.O. and Ogundele O.J.K. 2008 "Enhancing the Role of entrepreneurship in Creating Active Micro Business and SMES to Meet the Challenges of Vision 2020' Being a

paper presented at the conference organised by the Faculty of Management Sciences (FMS)
Nnamdi Azikwe University

Theme: Managing Nigerian's Micro Business and Small Medium Scale Enterprises (SMES) for
Active participation in the Global Economy at the University of Auditorium Nnamdi Azikwe
University Awka Anambra State. April 9-11, 2008

Olayiwola, P.O. 2007 Social Economic Implications of Rural Urban Drift in Nigeria. Journal
of Social Policy Vol.

Olorunlogbon A. C. 2008 The Role of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Employment
Generation in Nigeria A Study of Oshodi-Isole Local Government area in Lagos State being a
Research project Submitted to Distance Learning Institute in partial fulfilment for the award -
of B.Sc in Business Administration University of Lagos

Olorunshola J.A. 2003 'Problems and Prospects of Small and Medium-Scale Industries in
Nigeria' Central Bank of Nigeria Training Centre Lagos No 4 pp 34-49

Zakari, I.M. 2006 Entrepreneurship: Prospects and Challenges" Institute of Chartered
Accountants of Nigeria, Student Journal January and March.